

A Review: Understanding the Entrepreneurial Behaviour of Farmers

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ABSTRACT

This study is a literature review on agricultural entrepreneurship, often known as Agripreneurship. Agripreneurship is an opportunity and a necessity for improving the production and profitability in agriculture and the allied sector. Agripreneurship needs hours to make agriculture a more attractive and profitable venture. The review focuses on entrepreneurial behaviour in the agriculture industry. The study is based on agripreneurial behaviour or related publications, primarily journals and scholarly articles. This paper is simply a review of the existing literature of more than 50 papers found on the entrepreneurial behaviour of farmers, mainly focusing on which attributes various researchers include while defining entrepreneurial behaviour in the agricultural sector often known as Agripreneurial behaviour. The findings of this paper will help us gain a better understanding of agribusiness behaviour and concentrate on agricultural entrepreneurship and how it might expand market opportunities and stimulate economic growth and development, particularly in agro-based economies.

KEYWORDS: Entrepreneurial behaviour, Agripreneurship, Agripreneurial behaviour, farmers.

INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurs are vital to a country's financial success and innovation. Entrepreneurship is defined as a collection of behaviours involving initiating and managing the reallocation of financial resources to create value (Herron & Robinson, 1993). Entrepreneurship is the practice of discovering market opportunities before devoting actions and resources to capitalising on such opportunities for long-term personal gain (Uddin & Bose, 2012). "Entrepreneurship generates new ideas, allows people to work for themselves, and promotes economic development, innovation, job creation, and social progress" (Turker & Selcuk, 2009). Agriculture continues to be the most critical sector of the Indian economy, playing a crucial role in accomplishing many development goals such as food security, income generation, job creation, and industrial development (Iffat, 2022). Agripreneurship is a synonym for agricultural entrepreneurship. It refers to the formation of agribusinesses in farming and associated sectors. (Bairwa et al., 2014). Entrepreneurial behaviour has risen considerably in recedes as a stimulus for development in many nations with developing socioeconomic tendencies. Entrepreneurial behaviour can be identified as a significant contributor to the growth of entrepreneurs (Landge S, Hatey A, Rathod PK, Nikam TR). According to empirical research, entrepreneurial behaviour functions as a person's attributes and the environment (Chell et al., 1992). This entrepreneurship process encompasses at least two concepts: occupational and behavioural. The farmer refers to "owning and operating a firm on one's account and risk," while "entrepreneurial behaviour in the sense of seizing an economic opportunity" (Sternberg & Wennekers, 2005). Future agripreneurship research should be performed in agro-based continents, according to (Benjamin 2018), because agricultural entrepreneurial research has the potential to spur technical improvement, economic expansion, and sustainability. Individuals' entrepreneurial behaviour influences their surroundings (Shane et al., 2003). Some experts have related agricultural entrepreneurship to expanding the non-agricultural sector by established farmers. (Seuneke et al., 2013). According to some authors, agricultural activity gives entrepreneurial prospects such as product development (e.g., organic farming and functional foods) and improvements to business processes, distribution, and marketing., (AEI-AGRI, 2016)). However, while comparing agricultural entrepreneurship to that of other industries, it is essential to remember that the farm sector has unique environmental and economic characteristics. (Pindado & Sánchez, 2017). The

agri-entrepreneurs, also known as Agripreneurs , Agripreneurship(, and to identify entrepreneurial behaviour in the agricultural sector, also known as agripreneural behaviour. According to (G McElwee 2004) farmers are those who work part-time or full-time in the agricultural industry. They focus on the farm and agriculture as their primary source of income, cultivating the land, growing crops, and keeping cattle. When it comes to rural enterprise and entrepreneurship, research has tended to focus on individual dynamics and behaviours, focusing on farmers as entrepreneurs (Article, 2013; McElwee, 2008). If we take farmers as entrepreneurs, we consider all activities other than farming and focus on an individual's behaviour. In this regard, farmers must recognize business opportunities and plan strategically. Farmers can learn new tactics and strategies to help them develop a successful business. Cooperation and networking skills, inventive abilities, and a willingness to take chances are required for realizing business potential. This perspective is typically by the findings on entrepreneurship (Article, 2013). The personal characteristics of an agri-entrepreneur have a significant impact on agribusiness.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

IS ENTREPRENEURIAL BEHAVIOUR DIFFERENT FROM AGRIPRENEURIAL BEHAVIOUR?

To be considered an agripreneur, one must engage in a variety of agricultural operations, such as growing and harvesting crops, raising livestock, or creating new products and services. In general, agripreneurs should be proactive and curious in their approach to their profession. They should also have strong managerial and organisational abilities.”(Bairwa et al., 2014). Agripreneurship and entrepreneurship are similar in exploring opportunities, motivation, risk-taking abilities, and the desire to succeed. Nonetheless, the first has a unique character distinct from the agricultural sector. (Bannor et al., 2021; Lans et al., 2017; Pindado & Sánchez, 2017). The answer depends on the study topic and research paradigm used(Pindado & Sánchez, 2017). Opportunities, proactiveness, risk-taking ability, and entrepreneurial self-efficacy are all characteristics of entrepreneurship that appear to be universal and independent of circumstance(Rauch et al., 2009). Entrepreneurial behaviour is directly concerned with understanding, predicting, and controlling human behaviour in enterprises. (McAdam & Cunningham, 2019). If the same is taken in agriculture, it is called Agripreneural behaviour. The following characteristics can be considered when considering agricultural entrepreneurship. Empirical research suggests that personal and environmental factors

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influence entrepreneurial behaviour. (Chell et al., 1992) .According to (Misra & Kumar, 2000), two significant elements can influence entrepreneurial behaviour: demographic and psychological characteristics. Using demographic data, we were able to create a typical entrepreneur profile. Family background, birth order, age, parental educational level, sex, marital status, previous employment experience, and so on have all been investigated as part of this plan. (Is et al., n.d.) Independence, ambition, setting one's own goals, innovation, and daring were the most highly regarded values related to entrepreneurial behaviour. According to the meaning assigned to these values, entrepreneurial behaviour is self-determined, self-motivated, and self-disciplined (Kirkley, 2016). Entrepreneurial psychology has its own set of psychological traits such as achievement motive, locus of control, risk-taking, and values; academics attempted to distinguish entrepreneurs from the general population. Desirability, feasibility, and optimism are strong predictors of recognising the chance to be an entrepreneur. However, a warm environment and taking part in apprenticeship and training programmes are the most direct ways to take advantage of business opportunities in farming (Yaseen et al., 2018).

DISCUSSING AGRIPRENEURIAL BEHAVIOUR.

“The constellation of functions, processes, and behaviours involved in the perception of opportunities and the formation of organisations is known as entrepreneurial behaviour” (Misra & Kumar, 2000). Agricultural entrepreneurial behaviour is also known as Agriprenrurial behaviour. There is no agreed-upon definition of entrepreneurial behaviour in the literature. The term "agripreneurial behaviour" is used in this study to refer to the ability or knowledge of a firm's fundamental elements. So various elements taken by different authors to conducting studies on entrepreneurial behaviour in the agriculture sector. “Risk-taking, accomplishment motivation, innovativeness, decision-making ability, information-seeking behaviour, coordinating ability, self-confidence, cosmopolites, and planning ability were all investigated as aspects of entrepreneurial activity” (Benjamin, 2018). “ The practical five entrepreneurial skills identified in the study (Kwasi et al., 2021) include the need for achievement, the need for autonomy, creative tendency, calculated risk-taking, and locus of control”. Cabbage farmers in Kiminini have shown trends of entrepreneurial behaviour such as autonomy, risk-taking, need for achievement, creativity and locus of control(Wanyonyi & Bwisa, 2015). Effective entrepreneurial behaviour involves high planning ability and decision-making ability. “. In their study, these nine components were also used by (Mandala et al., 2021). The original

entrepreneurial orientation concept contains three essential characteristics of entrepreneurial behaviour: innovativeness, risk-taking, and proactiveness. (Miller, 1983). (Willock et al., 1999) stated that Farmers' behaviour is influenced by the following attitudes: agricultural achievement, legislation, pessimism, openness in farming, financial risk, chemical use, and policy measurement. The respondents' entrepreneurial behaviour was examined using a scale developed by (R. R. CHAUDHARI, L. V. HIREVENKANAGOUDAR, S. N. HANCHINAL, A. N. MOKASHI & Department, 2007), which included nine dimensions: innovativeness, achievement motivation, decision-making ability, risk-orientation, coordination ability, planning ability, information-seeking behaviour, cosmopolites, and self-confidence. Innovativeness, accomplishment drive, decision-making ability, risk-exposure, coordination ability, planning ability, information-seeking behaviour, and self-confidence were identified to be the essential aspects of the entrepreneurial activity of dairy farmers. "The entrepreneurial behaviour of dairy farmers comprised nine components: innovativeness, achievement motivation, decision-making ability, risk orientation, coordinating ability, planning ability, information seeking, cosmopolites and self-confidence" (Benjamin, 2018).

➤ **RISK-TAKING ABILITIES**

Agripreneurs can take risks and always look for new information in agriculture. (Bairwa et al., 2014). Several researchers (Murali K. & Jhamtani A., 2003; Singh et al., 2013) had different conclusions on farmers' risk orientation; most of the farmers, they concluded, were at a medium risk level. On the contrary, they found (Abeyrathne & Jayawardena 2014) that Farmers have a relatively low-risk orientation. On measured risk-taking, the majority of farmers had low to medium scores. (Bannor et al., 2021). Policymakers should be aware that the environment and training they get significantly impact how they perceive and exploit agricultural business opportunities. (Yaseen et al., 2018).

➤ **ACHIEVEMENT MOTIVATION**

A person's inner will, an instinct of intention that propels them to action, is motivation. According to (Chaurasiya et al., 2016; RATHOD PRAKASH KUMART.R. NIKAM, 2012; Singh et al., 2013) most dairy farmers showed a medium degree of achievement motivation, with only a small percentage having a low or high level of motivation. Most of the researchers followed the same result. On the contrary, the majority had an increased need for achievement (Bannor et al., 2021).

➤ **INNOVATIVENESS-OPPORTUNITIES RECOGNITION AND EXPLOITATION\CREATIVITY**

According to Schumpeter, an entrepreneur can make money by introducing successful innovations. (Serrat, 2017). Most researchers believe that developing opportunities is the key to entrepreneurial behaviour. (Shane & Venkataraman, 2000), concentrating on how businesses explore you and take advantage of entrepreneurial opportunities. The most important aspects of the entrepreneurial process were identified as recognising and exploiting opportunities. (Shane & Venkataraman, 2000). Most of the dairy farmers had a medium level of innovativeness. This clearly shows that most respondents are interested in implementing new technology and methods in agricultural enterprise management.

➤ **DECISION-MAKING ABILITY**

The cognitive process that leads to selecting a belief or a course of action from a collection of alternatives is known as decision-making. Decision-making ability can be thought of as a problem-solving activity that ends with a satisfactory answer (Ahuja et al., 2017). According to (Boruah et al., 2015; Chaurasiya et al., 2016), most farmers have moderate decision-making capacity, followed by high inadequate decision-making ability and low strong decision-making ability. The same result was confirmed by (Ahmed et al., 2011; R. R. CHAUDHARI, L. V. HIREVENKANAGOUDAR, S. N. HANCHINAL, and A. N. MOKASHI & Department, 2007). According to many studies, only a small percentage of farmers have low to good decision-making abilities, while most farmers have middling decision-making abilities. Farmers with a higher educational level, more vital communication skills, a higher annual income, and a medium-sized land holding account for this (Benjamin, 2018).

➤ **INFORMATION SEEKING BEHAVIOR**

A user of information establishes expectations for formal or informal sources or services to meet his or her perceived need, which may or may not be met based on the user's requirements. (Boruah et al., 2015; Manivannanan & Tripathi, 2007; Wilson, 1999) stated in their study that most dairy farmers had a medium level of information-seeking behaviour, followed by those with high and low levels of information-seeking behaviour. Most farmers had a medium level of information-seeking followed by a low and high level (Chaurasiya et al., 2016). On the other hand, (Acheampong et al., 2017) found out that most rice farmers in

Ghana had a high level of information-seeking behaviour to better use information to increase productivity and raise living standards. All results were confirmed by (Benjamin 2018).

➤ **COORDINATING ABILITY/COMMUNICATION SKILL**

"Coordination" refers to establishing communication channels between persons working on various projects. (Vanagas & Stankevič, 2015). It was discovered by (Boruah et al., 2015) that the majority per cent of respondents had a moderate level of coordinating ability, followed by those who had an inadequate level of coordinating power and who had a good group of coordinating knowledge is possible that their lack of coordination may have been because to of the fact that most of the respondents had only completed secondary school, had a medium herd size and had a medium level of dairy farming knowledge.

SELF-CONFIDENCE /SELF AUTONOMY

To describe one's sense of self-confidence is to express trust in one's judgement, ability or power. to (Ahmed et al., 2011), most respondents had a medium degree of self-confidence, followed by a high level of self-confidence and a low level of self-confidence. This finding agrees with (Chaurasiya et al., 2016). There was also a link between self-confidence and exposure to extension services and literacy levels based on school level. A farmer's confidence level is determined by the number of years he has been educated. (Ahmed et al., 2011).

➤ **PLANNING ABILITIES**

Planning abilities are classified as thinking about and successfully managing activities to achieve specific goals with any available resources. The majority of academics conclude that most farmers have a moderate ability to plan forward. (Avhad et al., 2015). " According to (Boruah et al., 2015; Chaurasiya et al., 2016), most respondents had a moderate degree of planning ability, followed by a lousy level of planning ability, and finally, a good level of planning ability" (Abeyrathne & Jayawardena, 2014). All results were confirmed by (Benjamin 2018). Old age, limited training experience, marginal soil, and a modest animal holding with little exposure to modern dairy farming practices may lead to low planning activities. (Benjamin, 2018).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is a literature review on Agripreneurship. The study focuses on farmers' entrepreneurial behaviour, often known as agripreneurial behaviour. The analysis is based on

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more than 50 scholarly journals and articles on the entrepreneurial behaviour of farmers and related themes.

4. DISCUSSION:

Agripreneurship's development in rural regions is now being viewed to improve rural people's socioeconomic status and economy. According to the study's findings, most farmers have a medium entrepreneurship degree. The same was confirmed by (Benjamin 2018); according to a survey, most respondents had a medium to a low degree of entrepreneurial behaviour (Bannor et al., 2021).with only a handful having a high level of entrepreneurial behaviour. (Subrahmanyeswari & Veeraraghava Reddy, 2007) . According to (Ataei et al., 2021), Only two criteria - risk-taking and advancement motivation were shown to be important-significantly affected the entrepreneurial behaviour process. Farmers' entrepreneurial behaviour improved as their socioeconomic status and social involvement improved. (Abeyrathne & Jayawardena, 2014). A farmer's entrepreneurial behaviour is essential because, as an entrepreneur, they take risks in cultivating and marketing their food—the need for farmers to increase their decision-making abilities and level of farming innovation. Farmers must assume risk to face any problems (Wanyonyi & Bwisa, 2015). Researchers and policymakers believe that gaining a better understanding of agricultural entrepreneurship could be a critical instrument for contributing to the sector's vitality and competitiveness and the vitality and competitiveness of rural communities(AEI-AGRI, 2016). According to a literature survey, the agriculture sector is disregarded in general entrepreneurship research(Alsos et al., 2011). HOWEVER, recent CAP (standard agriculture policies) adjustments have favoured more market-oriented agriculture, as previously said, and farmers must enhance their entrepreneurial behaviour. (Vesala & Vesala, 2010) . According to the findings (Ahuja et al., 2016), most dairy farmers had moderate entrepreneurial tendencies. Entrepreneurial behaviour relied heavily on cosmopolitanism, coordinating abilities, and a desire to succeed. India must quickly create entrepreneurial human resources to promote entrepreneurial behaviours to establish a developed economy and deal with the problem of unemployment. Scholars emphasise the importance of individual behaviour in understanding business prospects and performing entrepreneurship functions, such as resource organisation, creativity, rent-seeking behaviour, and risk tolerance. Individual behaviour reflects how people pay attention to changes in developing countries, where options are plentiful and varied. Even so, a friendly environment and culture are vulnerable (Lingelbach et al., 2011). According to (Ahuja et al., 2017), most

dairy farmers have a medium level of decision-making ability and risk orientation. Most research has concentrated on general entrepreneurial behaviour, overlooking the critical importance of context in entrepreneurship. As a result, it's crucial to pay attention to the unique characteristics of entrepreneurial behaviour in a particular setting. This study focuses on agriculture entrepreneurs, agripreneurs, agricultural entrepreneurial behaviour, or agripreneurial behaviour (Robert et al., 2016; Zahra and Wright, 2011). According to the findings, most respondents had a moderate level of entrepreneurial behaviour. The first three components contributing to dairy farmers' entrepreneurial behaviour were cosmopolites, coordination ability and accomplishment motivation. (Ahuja et al., 2016). The majority of dairy farmers demonstrated a moderate level of entrepreneurial behaviour, which could be related to their medium degrees of innovativeness, accomplishment motivation, decision-making capacity, information-seeking behaviour, and cosmopolites as demonstrated by (Baindha et al., 2019; Chaurasiya et al., 2016). The majority had a high need for achievement. In contrast, internal locus of control scores is medium to high. However, most farmers have low to medium scores on other entrepreneurial attributes (need for autonomy, creative tendency and calculated risk-taking). According to the basis of a previous study, this study concluded that most respondents were a moderate level of entrepreneurial behaviour followed by a high and low level of entrepreneurial behaviour. Entrepreneurs will benefit from the contributions in this paper issue as they optimise their agricultural behaviours. The benefits of observing agricultural behaviours from a more holistic perspective that considers social development has been proven in this research.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

In this paper, the study is confined to components of the entrepreneurial behaviour of farmers only. Although in future studies, other components of entrepreneurial behaviour can be included. This study is entirely based on the literature. These considered the points generally taken by all authors while conducting the study. This paper revealed that it adds to the growing agricultural entrepreneurship research by incorporating information on farmers' entrepreneurial behaviour. For the agricultural industry to improve productivity and profitability, Agripreneurship needs to be a driving force.

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